

FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF PARTICULATE REINFORCED COMPOSITES: POLYMER BLENDS AND MMCs

R.D. Evans*, S. Tao*, W.E. Baker, and J.D. Boyd***

***Department of Materials and Metallurgical Engineering, Queen's University**

****Department of Chemistry, Queen's University**

ABSTRACT

The fracture behaviour of a brittle dispersed phase-ductile matrix polymer blend (PS-HDPE) and a metal matrix composite (Al/A356-SiC) have been studied and compared. Particular effort was made to test both materials at similar loading rates, and to have comparable ranges of particle sizes. For the polymer blends, the interfacial bonding was varied by adding a reactive copolymer in varying concentrations

Both composite materials exhibit large decreases in fracture toughness compared with the unreinforced matrix material. This trend can be reversed in reactive polymer blends where J_{IC} increases with increasing concentration of surface reactivity. In MMCs containing large particles ($> 10 \mu\text{m}$), particle distributions are highly non-uniform, and fracture is controlled by particle cracking and the degree of particle clustering. In MMCs containing small particles ($< 3 \mu\text{m}$), the fracture mechanism appears similar to that in the highly reactive polymer blends. The fracture surfaces in both materials exhibit limited interface decohesion and gross plastic deformation in the matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Polymer blends and metal matrix composites (MMCs) are 2 examples of particulate reinforced composites. Generally, polymer blends are produced by adding a rubber dispersed phase to a brittle or semi-ductile matrix, for the purpose of improving on the fracture toughness of the pure matrix material. However, there have been recent studies of blends of a brittle dispersed polymer phase in a ductile polymer matrix [1,2]. The strength and stiffness of such blends are raised, but the limiting property becomes the toughness which generally decreases with increasing volume fraction of dispersed phase. In polymer blends the interfacial bonding can be controlled by the addition of a reactive copolymer. If the interfacial bond is sufficiently strong, the decrease in toughness with increasing dispersed phase can be arrested or even reversed (Fig. 1).

MMCs have ceramic particulate in a ductile metal matrix. Again, the increase in strength and stiffness is offset by the decrease in toughness. The fracture toughness of MMCs has been shown to depend on the volume fraction, particle size, and particle distribution of the dispersed phase [3,4]. There is not such clear evidence of the effect of interface bond strength on the

toughness of MMCs, as there is for reactive polymer blends. MMCs produced by molten metal processing have strong chemical bonding at the interface due to reaction between the 2 phases. Small increases in ductility have been reported for MMCs containing oxide-coated particulate which have lower interfacial strengths than uncoated particulate [5,6].

The fracture mechanisms in the 2 classes of materials are quite different. In polymer blends, fracture is initiated by either particle cavitation, matrix shear yielding, or matrix crazing. In MMCs, the fracture process is dominated by particle cracking or interface decohesion, especially in closely-spaced particle clusters. The specific effect of interfacial bond strength on the fracture mechanisms is not well understood for either material.

The current study compares the fracture behaviour of a brittle dispersed phase -ductile matrix polymer blend and an MMC. Particular effort was made to test both materials at similar loading rates, and to have comparable ranges of particle sizes. For the polymer blends, the interfacial bonding was varied by adding a reactive copolymer in varying concentrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

The polymer blends were made by blending Sclair high density polyethylene (HDPE) 2907 with preformed polystyrene (PS) particulate. The PS particles had a lightly crosslinked PS core and a methacrylic acid surface functionality. Interfacial reaction between the matrix and particulate was promoted through the addition of a functionalized copolymer, HDPE with glycidyl methacrylate (GMA) functional groups grafted to the backbone. The details of the blending technique are given elsewhere [2]. Blends were prepared containing 0 - 20 volume percent particles having mean diameters of 0.3, 1.2, and 4.0 μm , and 0 - 20 volume percent of the reactive copolymer. In all, 18 different blends were prepared.

Fracture toughness of the polymer blends was measured using the J-integral test. The procedure described in ASTM E813 was followed, with the modification given by So and Broutman [7]. Three-point bend single-edge notched (3PB-SEN) beams measuring 12 mm x 4 mm x 130 mm were moulded on a Mining and Chemical Products Ltd. MCP 100SA bench top moulding machine at 180 °C. A centre notch was cut with a 45° multi-tooth cutter, and precracking was initiated by pressing a surgical razor blade into the centre of the milled notch. All J-integral tests were carried out on a Sintech 2/G Universal testing machine. J-integral tests were conducted at -20 °C at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. These values were chosen based on results reported in the literature for HDPE [8].

The samples were deformed to different strains, stained, and unloaded. Prior to unloading, the crosshead was stopped and BDH Oil Red O dye was injected onto the fracture surface. Samples were fractured after immersion in liquid nitrogen and the fracture surfaces were examined with a scaled optical microscope. The crack extension, Δa , was measured at the point of greatest crack extension, generally at the mid-thickness of the sample. The J-value for each sample was calculated using the expression

$$J = \frac{2U}{B(W-a)}, \quad (1)$$

where U is the energy absorbed up to the point of unloading, B=the sample width, W=the sample depth, and a=the initial crack length. J-values were plotted against Δa for each sample. To allow for elastic deformation of the sample, the theoretical blunting line was calculated using eqn. 2. The tensile yield strength, σ_y , was measured for each sample with the same test conditions used for J-integral tests.

$$J=2\sigma_y\Delta a \quad (2)$$

J_{IC} was determined from the intersection of the blunting line with a least-squares regression fitted line through the experimentally determined J vs Δa data.

MMC samples of A356 aluminum alloy (Al-7Si-0.35Mg) were prepared by squeeze casting. Two different particulate sizes were employed, 15 μm and 3 μm . The starting material for the 15 μm MMC samples was a commercially cast billet of A356 + 15 volume percent SiC ("Duralcan"). Volume percent SiC was varied from 5-15% by remelting the starting material, diluting the melt with unreinforced A356 and squeeze casting as 80 mm diameter x 35 mm height cylindrical blocks [4]. The 3 μm SiC material was prepared by pressure infiltrating molten A356 into a preform of mixed SiC and Al powders [9]. Particle size and particle spacing distributions were determined for all MMC materials by optical metallography and an automatic tessellation technique [10].

Fracture toughness of the MMCs was measured by 4-point bend tests on double edge notched samples. Blanks for the 10 mm x 10 mm x 78 mm bend samples were cut from the squeeze cast blocks with their long axis perpendicular to the casting direction, machined to final dimensions, and 4.5 mm deep notches having approximately 45 μm root radius cut by electro-discharge machining. The bend tests were carried out on an Instron universal testing machine at a line displacement rate of 0.005 mm/s. K_{IC} values were calculated from the expression

$$K_{IC} = \frac{3Pe\sqrt{a}}{db^2} f\left(\frac{a}{b}\right), \quad (3)$$

where P =the load, e =eccentricity, a =crack length, b =height, and d =width. The region of the uncracked notch was examined to determine the nature and extent of damage prior to fracture. Both the pre-polished outside surface and repolished sections at midthickness were examined by optical metallography and SEM. Tensile samples, 4 mm diameter and 14 mm gauge length, were machined with the tensile axis perpendicular to the squeeze casting direction, and tensile tests were carried out at a crosshead speed of 0.005 mm/s.

A third batch of MMC material was pure Al-10 vol% SiC prepared by hot extrusion of preforms of Al powder and SiC particulate. Samples were prepared having SiC particle diameter of 0.8 μm , 3 μm , and 12 μm . Only tensile tests were carried out on this material.

The fracture surfaces of both polymer blends and MMCs were examined by SEM.

RESULTS

HDPE-PS POLYMER BLENDS

The variation in J_{IC} with vol. pct. PS particulate in an unreactive HDPE matrix is shown in Fig. 2. With increasing vol. pct. particulate there is a continuous decrease in J_{IC} from the pure HDPE value. The decrease in J_{IC} is somewhat less for larger particles, but still significant.

The variation in J_{IC} with wt. pct. of the reactive copolymer (HDPE-g-GMA) in the matrix for 20% particulate is shown in Fig. 3. With increasing interface reactivity, there is a recovery

in J_{IC} values compared with those for the unreactive matrix. At 20% of 1.2 μm particulate, $J_{IC}=0.80 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ for 20% reactivity, compared with 0.41 kJ/m^2 for 0% reactivity. i.e. the percent decrease in J_{IC} with the addition of 20% particulate is reduced from 67% to 36%. Again, the J_{IC} values for the larger particle size are slightly higher. The variation in J_{IC} with wt. pct. matrix reactivity and particle size appears to correlate with the number of available sites for covalent bonding at the interface. The number of GMA mers available for bonding per unit area of the interface was calculated for all of the reactive blends, and the J_{IC} values were plotted against this quantity (Fig. 4). There is a general trend to increasing J_{IC} with increasing GMA mers/ μm^2 of interface.

The fracture surfaces of the bend test samples show predominantly matrix shear yielding for the highly reactive blends (Fig. 5) and matrix crazing for unreactive blends (Fig. 6) [11].

A356-SiC AND Al-SiC MMCs

Fig. 7 shows the variation in K_{IC} with vol. fraction of particulate for the 15 μm A356-SiC MMC. There is a sharp decrease in K_{IC} with addition of particulate, but there is little change in K_{IC} with vol. fraction over the range 5-15%. This material has a highly clustered particle distribution. Damage, in the form of particle cracking and interface decohesion is concentrated in particle clusters. Hence, K_{IC} depends on local parameters (eg. nearest neighbour spacing distribution and local volume fraction) and not on mean values of volume fraction.

The particle distribution in the 3 μm A356-SiC material is much more uniform. With decreasing particle size there is a transition in damage mechanism from particle cracking to interface decohesion. In the 3 μm material, damage is predominantly interface decohesion. A similar transition in damage mechanism is observed in the Al-10%SiC MMC samples. The particle distribution is uniform at all particle sizes in this material and the damage mechanism changes from particle cracking in the 12 μm material to interface decohesion in the 0.8 μm material. However, there is little effect of particle size on measured values of fracture toughness or ductility in any of the MMC materials. The K_{IC} values are similar for the 15 μm and 3 μm samples of A356-15%SiC (Fig. 7), and there is little variation in ductility with particle size for the samples of Al-10%SiC [12].

DISCUSSION

Notwithstanding the basic differences in the 2 types of materials, there are some remarkable similarities in the fracture behaviours. Both exhibit large decreases in fracture toughness of the composite materials compared with the unreinforced matrix material. The fracture toughness generally decreases with increasing volume fraction of particulate. By comparison, the effect of particle size on fracture toughness is small.

For large particles (i.e. $> 10 \mu\text{m}$) the fracture behaviour of MMCs is quite different. In these materials, particle distributions can be highly non-uniform, and fracture involves the cumulative development of damage by particle cracking in clustered regions and linking of the "damage clusters" by ductile fracture in the matrix. The fracture toughness is strongly influenced by the degree of particle clustering.

However, for MMCs containing small particles ($< 3\mu\text{m}$), where the particle distributions are uniform and particle cracking is absent, the fracture mechanism appears to have some similarities to that in the polymer blends. The fracture surfaces of these MMCs (Fig. 10) and the reactive polymer blends (Fig. 7) both exhibit limited interface decohesion and gives plastic

deformation in the matrix. More data on damage, fracture toughness and fracture mechanisms should be obtained for these specific materials to develop a generic fracture model for particulate reinforced composites.

The most striking difference between the 2 types of composite materials is the possibility of controlling the interface strength in the reactive polymer blends, and the significant effect this has on fracture toughness. It is not possible to vary the interface strength in MMCs to the same degree. However, the similarity of the fracture morphologies for the small particle MMCs and the reactive polymer blends indicate that the interface strength in these MMCs is relatively high.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to H. Teng and Y.L. Liu of Riso National Laboratory, Denmark for providing the Al-SiC MMC material. This research is supported financially by the Ontario Centre for Materials Research.

REFERENCES

1. T. Liu, H. Xie, W. Baker, A. Rudin and K. O'Callaghan, *J. Polym. Sci. Pt. B Polym. Phys.*, **31**, p. 1347 (1993)
2. R.D. Evans, W.E. Baker, J.D. Boyd and T. Pith, *Submitted to J. Mat. Eng. Sci*
3. D.J. Lloyd, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, **39**, p. 59 (1991)
4. S. Tao and J.D. Boyd, in Mechanisms and Mechanics of Composites Fracture, Eds. R.D. Bhagat, S.G. Fishman and R.J. Arsenault, ASM, p. 29 (1993)
5. H. Ribes, R. Da Silva, M. Suéry and T. Bretheau, *Mater. Sci. Tech.*, **6**, p. 621 (1990)
6. Y.H. Teng and J.D. Boyd, *Composites*, **25**, p.906 (1994)
7. P.K. So and L.J. Broutman, *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, **26**, p. 1173 (1986)
8. M.K.V. Chan and J.G. Williams, *Int. Jour. Frac.*, **19**, p. 145 (1983)
9. S. Tao and J.D. Boyd, Recent Developments in Light Metals, Eds. M. Gilbert, E.O. Ozberk and P. Tremblay, CIM, p. 113 (1994)
10. S. Tao, N. Townley and J.D. Boyd, *Microstructural Science*, in press (1995)
11. L.A. MacGillivray, 4th Year Thesis, Queen's University (1995)
12. S. Tao, Y.H. Teng and J.D. Boyd, unpublished research.

Figure 1. Toughening of PMMA-PE Blends Through Reactive Compatibilization[1]

Figure 2. Decrease in J_{IC} with Addition of PS Particles to an Unreactive HDPE Matrix

Figure 3. Recovery of J_{IC} with Reactive Compatibilization of a PS-HDPE Blend

Figure 4. Variation in J_{IC} with Reactive Site Concentration for PS-HDPE Blends

Figure 5. Fracture Surface of a Reactive PS-HDPE Blend Showing Matrix Shear Yielding[12]

Figure 6. Fracture Surface of an Unreactive PS-HDPE Blend Showing Matrix Crazing[12]

Figure 7. Variation on K_{IC} with Particle Volume Fraction for A356-SiC MMCs

Figure 8. Fracture Surface of an Al-10%SiC (0.8 μm particle diameter) Showing Interface Decohesion and Ductile Fracture in Matrix [11]